

ISic3425

I.Sicily inscription 3425

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

ash chest

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2014.09

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

area of Grotticelli, podere Randazzo

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 16210

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text**Apparatus****Translation****Commentary****Digital identifiers:**

TM 644820

Bibliography

Orsi, P. 1900. Frammenti epigrafici sicelioti. *Rivista di storia antica*. 5: 39-66. At 63 no.42

Ferrua, A 1941. Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. *Rivista di archeologia cristiana*. 18: 151-243. At 217 no.98

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